

INFLUENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE ON THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION IN NIGERIAN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS.

By

KOLEDADE, BOLANLE FUNMILAYO

*School of Basic and Remedial Studies,
Kwara State College of Education Ilorin, Kwara State.*

Abstract

Language is essentially a characteristic of human being. Language is used, among other human tools, to communicate; in essence to make meaning. Communication or miscommunication, whichever use a language is put to a large extent, has an impact on the society. The form and status of English as a second language in Nigeria have attracted the interest of scholars both in Nigeria and in other parts of the world. Though, there are many areas of disagreement among scholars on the issue of form and status of English in Nigeria, it is generally held that English as it is in Nigeria today, is the product of an interplay of factors, ranging from socio-cultural to linguistic arising from the contact between English and the Nigeria languages in Nigeria's multilingual environment. It is now an established fact that English which initially was introduced to the Nigeria environment as a foreign language was later shaped and transformed by subsequent developments into a second language with an official status. In essence, interlingual transfer is what is foregrounded in the extract where elements are carried from one language into another. This work therefore examines the influence of mother tongue on English language, the endless conflict this has generated on the Nigeria sociolinguistic terrain of learning in tertiary institutions with possible recommendations.

Keywords: *Mother tongue, English Language, Medium of Instruction Nigerian Tertiary Institutions.*

Introduction

English Language in Nigeria could be traced back to the 18th century when indigenes living on the territory came into contact with British settlers.

Consequently, its formal teacher dated back to the 17th century when the missionary established schools purposely to train the indigenes on how to interpret English Language speech, read Bible with average proficiency. As from then, English language has gained a superior role in Nigeria. It is not only spoken by the elite but it has become so entrenched on them that its uses penetrates every fabric of our national life. According to Fafunwa (1986) cited in Suleiman (1997), English Language being an official language in the country has made it a pivot factor in national awareness. It is the language of administration, education and the mass media. English Language has a dominant position in all official transactions, higher education, science and technology, the media, the legislative as well as the judiciary. English is spoken as a MOTHER TONGUE (and official language) by over four hundred million people in Britain, most parts of the United States of America and Canada, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa and many parts of the West Indies i.e. those countries that were formerly under the British Empire. In the European Mainland, the Middle East, and in many parts of Asia and South America, English is the most widely preferred FOREIGN LANGUAGE. This is why the English language is often referred to as the world's "lingua franca." English has today, become the principal lingual Franca of educated Nigerians, the principal medium of instruction in Nigeria's educational system. Therefore, being an official means of communication in Nigeria, it is highly necessary to improve the official communication skills of the students' pupils in order to enhance both the written and spoken version of it.

History of the English Language

The English Language has not always been what it is. It has over the ages, undergone several changes and transformations both in form and content. These changes have been due to several factors, both internal and

external. In this work, we shall attempt a brief account of the evolution of the English Language from the beginning. Also, we will consider the many forces that are responsible for the rise and growth of the language, by examining the periods of demarcation in its development, the influences brought to bear on the language as well as the main landmarks in its history.

The part of the world known as Britain today prior to 43 AD, was occupied by a group of people called the CELTS, whose origin was not known. However, it is from this point that the history of the English people and language is often taken, although it was sometimes thought that the Celts themselves were invaders of the island many centuries before, and they tended to exist in clusters.

Along with German and Dutch, English is said to have descended from the West Germanic Language family which, together with East and North Germanic Languages (which gave birth to such languages as Gothic and Danish, Swedish and Norwegian respectively), are all descendants of the Germanic Languages. It is believed that these Germanic Languages themselves descended from the Proto-Indo-European Languages which existed as long ago as 2000 B.C. It is reported that the Indo-European influences can be found in the structure and in the vocabulary of the language used even today. They include the division of words into various parts of speech, as well as the fact that many words in these Germanic languages share common nuclei, take stress on the first syllable or near the beginning and accept the two-tense system.

The first known and recorded conquerors of the Celts were the Romans who occupied the land from 43–410 AD and administered the Celt area as an overseas country. During this time, Rome introduced Latin as the official language and produced many manuscripts in that language. Brief as this period was, this Latin influence has persisted till today. It left behind some linguistic influence such as names that end in the 'chester' (e.g. Manchester),

words like "straer" (street) "weal" (wall), "ceap" (cheap), "win" (wine), and also left behind some Latin scribes and missionaries, etc. However, due to constant harassment and threat from one Saxons. Angles and Jutes Pirates from North-West Europe of the Netherlands, Germany and Denmark, as well as the struggle with the Celts at home, Rome was forced to withdraw her forces.

On taking full possession of the land, the war-like Saxons, Angles and Jutes divided the Celt area among themselves by setting up small kingdoms which were all culturally linked. The invaders were all called "Saxons" and later the "Angles", while the land was known as Angeloynn. It later became England, "land of the Angles". The language was known as English but Latin continued to be used as the language of liturgy and literature.

During the period of occupation, many Celts were forced to move north and westward to develop or join existing kingdoms such as Wales, Scotland, Cornwall, etc. Linguistic influences of Celt origin which remain, though, as words such as "Crag", "Combe" are traces to the period. Place names such as "Thames", "Avon", "Exe...", "Wye..." "Dover", "Ken" etc. can also be traced to the Celt language. But the clusters of Celt kingdoms under the madders remained scattered until King Edgar of Wessex, the ruler of a kingdom in the Saxon area, unified them all through conquest and amalgamation. Gradually, the dialect of West Saxon became more prominent and emerged as the literacy dialect. Thus began a discernible period in the history of the people and language of England, the Anglo-Saxon period (Medubi, 2007).

Functions /Importance of Language

When we talk of language, we are discussing "human essence" because it is language that makes us "human"; in fact language develops human socially. A learned man makes social contacts with people, praises and rejoices with others through the appropriate use of language. There is no

development in human race without language. The animal kingdom remained what it had been since creation because of its inability to use language. Our society can only develop by building upon existing ideas, framework, infrastructures and research findings of many which exist in print.

Documentation for future use will be hard for a society without language. As long as there could be discoveries and inventions, without any manifest use of language, we believe that preservation, transmission and development of new ideas that resulted to major breakthrough in life might be difficult or even be impossible without language. The rich thoughts of great men and philosophers are preserved either in the oral or written forms of language.

Language determines and strengthens personality. What a person says, why he says it, is an index of his personality. A person's feelings about himself depend on his use of language, the response of others to his language and the feelings produced by the relationship with the crowd from his communication with others. With language, nations can gather under a common umbrella to reason, define, classify, generalize, make hypothesis and draw conclusion as well as mutual understanding and ensure peace, one can hopefully talk of a language approximating to world lingua franca.

The metalinguistic function of language is an important thing to discuss. Language is used in expressing itself, that is, we use English or any other language to discuss language. For instance, we use English to teach English language as a school subject just as the local language may be used to teach the students themselves in schools and colleges.

Finally, language plays a very significant role in learning and general education. It is the primary tool for acquiring knowledge of whichever type, be it formal or informal. Teachers in their business of imparting knowledge to learners, make learning meaningful through effective use of language. Without it, teaching and learning would not be achieved.

Objectives of English Language Today (ELT)

The objectives of teaching English language as stated in the National Policy on Education cited in (Enesi, 2004) includes:

- (1) Ability to speak fluent and acceptable English.
- (2) Ability to understand simple conversational spoken English at normal speed.
- (3) Ability to comprehend certain part at various level.
- (4) Ability to write clear, acceptable English on prescribed topics.

These are given to prove that the objectives of teaching English language in Nigeria as encompassed in the National Policy on Education (2004) are anything but realizable. The feasibility of realizing the objectives lie in re-appraising and ensuring implementation right from the grass root up to the higher level. This implementation of course, could only be done by the collective effort of only the trained specialized English language teachers. In recognition of the importance of English language for enhancing educational attainment as well as for improving communication ability of citizens, the government has made the subject a core subject. It is compulsory for students to have a credit in English language before entering any tertiary institution.

The Position of Language in the New Educational System

In language education, goals are usually determined by the role which a particular language is expected to play in and outside the school curriculum. The role of English language is therefore very important in the school curriculum. In curriculum planning, the vital function of English language must be noted so that the objectives of the National Policy on Education and the language Policy in particular will be realized. It was in recognition of the importance and contribution of mother tongue to education that made the Federal Ministry of Education in collaboration with other educational statutory

agencies include in the National Policy on Education (1977) revised in (1981), the use of mother tongue as a medium of educating pupils in the pre-primary and primary levels throughout the country.

The National Policy on Education (1977) revised in (1981), section 2 (i) states that: "Government will ensure that the medium of instruction will be principally the mother tongue or the language of the immediate community."

Also section 3 (xx) of the same National Policy states that: Government will see to it that the medium of instruction in the primary school is initially the mother tongue of the immediate community and at a later stage English.

The importance of Nigerian language in the educational process is stated in section 1:

In addition to appreciating the importance of language in educational process, and as a means of preserving people's culture, the government considers it in the best interest of national unity that each child should be encouraged to learn one of the three major languages other than his mother tongue.

When goals are blurred and conflicting with people's attitude to the language, the curriculum content, its methodology and mode of evaluation will be adversely affected. Any language may perform some of the following roles:

- a. **As the mother-tongue:** Mother-tongue is the child's language at birth, the language of the native community into which the child is born.
- b. **As the national language:** national language is characteristic of nation – states such as English in England, Swahili in Tanzania, Hebrew in Israel, Danish in Denmark, French in France and Amharic in Ethiopia.

c. **As official language:** This may be indigenous or foreign and it possesses utilization or functional value because it is used at government level for all communication as a working language.

d. **As language for specialized education:** For acquiring further knowledge and information without which the career of the individual involved is handicapped.

e. **As language for general education:** Such a language helps the learners broaden their world's outlook, for instance, the role of English in France or French in England. A language that serves this purpose enhances but does not constitute a pre-requisite for advancement.

f. **As language for Elite Education:** This is the language of the fraction of the population, especially those who are entrusted with the affairs of the nation. It is the language of mass communication or the mass media, but not the language of the masses.

g. **As Language of Assimilation:** This is associated with the colonial policy of cultural assimilation, for instance, French in the Francophone West African Countries.

An Overview of English in Nigeria

Though English in Nigeria has generated a lot of controversy especially from the perspective of the variant features it presents at the basic levels of language analysis, it is generally believed that the English which has emerged in the Nigerian environment is a new English having a distinctive Nigerian flavour. Many of the renowned scholars in this field believe that the English language has undergone an inevitable process of modification in the Nigerian environment which has subsequently transformed the language into a nativized variety. Bamgbose (1995), for example, is of the view that English has witnessed tremendous changes in the Nigerian environment. He notes that English in Nigeria has been nativized, acculturated and twisted to

express unaccustomed concepts and modes of interaction. Kujore (1985), one of the greatest contributors to the debate on English as a second language in Nigeria, sees the indigenization of English in Nigeria, not as a surprise, but as an expected development. He argues that English, as a living language, is bound to undergo changes in such a foreign environment as Nigeria's whose cultural and linguistic backgrounds are different from that of English in mother tongue (EMT) environment. Kachru (1982), believes that Nigerian English is a vital component of world Englishes which has been indigenized to suit local conditions, to express local experiences and to cater for the local Nigerian environment. Okonoda (1990) submits that language learnt in contact may often exhibit some kinds of language mixing, such that two languages mix up either in the same stretch of speech or at different times.

Jowitt (1991) opines that the English which is used in the Nigerian environment is something other than a replica of "native speakers" varieties. He warns, however, that English in Nigeria with all its "Nigerianism", should not be seen as evidence of the imperfect learning of the language but rather, as possible signs of healthy acculturation, and of the creative capacity normally associated with the learning and use of a mother tongue. The evolution of local varieties of English is an illustration of the adaptation of an overseas variety of English to meet the requirements of a second language context. In its use as a medium of both formal and informal communications, it needs to be "fine-tuned" to be capable of expressing the socio-cultural realities of that country. Some of these realities are expressed through modification of the phonological and grammatical systems of standard overseas English. The generation of new lexical and grammatical extensions to either reduce some of the local culture which cannot be covered by existing uses of English, are reflections of this Interlingua creativity. The lexis of a language may be extended by process of elaboration while the process of

reduction in the meaning of a lexical item is simplification (Wigwe, 1981). Studies in contrastive linguistics reveal that when a learner moves from his first language to the second language, the linguistic skills he has already internalized in the first language will be carried over into the second language situation (Weinreich, 1968; Lado, 1958). This is equally true of Nigeria where English is a second language. For instance, Oyeleye (1988) paints the picture of the Nigerian's bilingual situation clearly when he says that "it is not unlikely therefore that the Nigerian user of English may have transferred this linguistic habit of his first language to the second language". Naturally, speaker has acquired some amount of competence in the language such that all the working systems of the language have been internalized. As a result of this, "the learners" rooted knowledge of the two languages is not similar, and this inhibits the learning of the L₂.

The Nigerian English has characteristics which deviate markedly from "Standard English". This is because just as there are differences in the phonology and syntax, there are lexico-semantic differences between English and the indigenous Nigerian languages. Nigerian speakers of English therefore transfer the thoughts on their minds directly from their mother tongue into English.

The Concept of Mother Tongue/First Language (L₁)

One of the chief characteristics of human beings is the ability to communicate effectively. A normal human being achieves this exchange of information mainly by means of two types of sensory stimulation which are auditory and visual. A child begins to learn an auditory function from the environment in which he belongs. He responds to the sounds and tone, which his mother, father and elders habitually use in sending different messages to him. This acquired speech is what we call the mother tongue (MT), the first language (L₁), or the native language. This is simply the

language acquired in one's native environment and which meets all the linguistic needs.

The mother tongue (MT) is usually, sequentially the first language of a bilingual or multilingual person. It can also be said to mean the language which a bi-/multilingual person uses to conduct his everyday activities and of which he has the greatest linguistic facility or intuitive knowledge. In most cases, the MT is the language acquired unconsciously and naturally early in life. Later, a child learns its conventional visual version which is writing.

Influence of Mother Tongue on the Use of English Language in Nigeria Tertiary Institution

English, obviously, is the language of communication in our classrooms in Nigeria. Some have acquired communicative competence of the language right from home while some have their first contact with it in the classroom. When some Yoruba speakers of English language speak for instance, it is noticed that 'received' rhythm as well as some phonological features are not present. Instead, some features of the mother tongue (MT) are manifested in the speech. This phenomenon is simply called INTERFERENCE. This is the instance of deviations from the features of either language, which occurs in the speech of bilinguals as a result of their familiarity with the two languages. The term implies a re-arrangement of patterns that results from the introduction of foreign elements into a more highly structured domain of a language such as (bulk of) phonology, syntax as well as some areas of vocabulary, culture and discourse interference. In other words, it is a term which refers to situations whereby two different languages overlap in the speech of a bilingual. Basically, the interference of mother tongue in learning English is down to three basic concepts of phonetic. These concepts are articulatory, acoustic and auditory phonetics. Although, English language retains its dominant position in the education delivery system in Nigeria. The

thrust of our educational language policy is the use of the mother tongue or the language of the immediate community in pre-primary and primary education but conflict tend to appear since both are used at pre-primary and primary levels. When a speaker has come in contact with two or more languages, he or she may begin to use them together, although not with equal proficiency (Wikipedia, 2013).

Conclusion

This work is an over view of the influence of mother tongue on English Language as a medium of instruction in Nigeria tertiary institutions. Emphasis is layed on language contact phenomenon which is the characteristic of a bilingual or multilingual society. It discusses English as a second language in Nigeria. It dwells on the contact it had with the indigenous languages and the seemingly, endless conflict this has generated on the Nigerian sociolinguistic terrain of learning in tertiary institution. Emphasis has been placed on interference as a natural consequence of language contact situation with its impending problems toward the indigenization of English language in Nigeria as a reference point. As a result of this, the learners rooted knowledge of the two languages is not similar, and this inhibits the learning of the L₂.

Recommendations

- Only those who are professionally trained should be allowed to teach at our tertiary institutions.
- There should be no tribal discrimination among the students in our tertiary institutions.
- Seminars should be organized for teachers in English for an update to enhance their performance.
- The quality of spoken and written English language among school children should be highly encouraged.

- Improved methods of teaching English language in our tertiary institution in essential.
- A firm foundation in English language should be encouraged at an early stage in life.
- English language teachers in primary, senior primary, secondary and tertiary institution should not embark on the use of mother tongue to teach and explain English language.
- The teaching and learning of English should be more practical in our schools.
- Materials for learning the subject should be supplied/available.
- Finally, there should be a review in the language policy on education in Nigeria.

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